

Design optimization and virtual testing of a morphing aileron with high actuation bandwidth

Vittorio Cavalieri ¹, Alessandro De Gaspari ^{2,*}

Department of Aerospace Science and Technology, Politecnico di Milano, Via La Masa 34, 20156, Milano, Italy

ARTICLE INFO

Editor: Dr Mehdi Ghoreyshi

Keywords:

Compliant structures
Morphing wings
Dynamic actuation
Aerodynamic shape optimization
Topology optimization
Dynamic resonant system

ABSTRACT

One of the key strategies to make future aviation more sustainable is to improve the aerodynamic efficiency-to-weight ratio of aircraft while simultaneously reducing the energy required to actuate onboard control surfaces. This paper presents a novel morphing aileron, designed for a hybrid-electric regional aircraft, developed to replace a conventional aileron while providing multiple benefits. Unlike traditional ailerons, which are restricted to rigid-body rotation, a morphing aileron changes its external shape, enabling greater design flexibility. This shape-changing capability has been exploited to first optimize the external morphed shapes of the aileron that match the aerodynamic performance of the conventional surface, while requiring half the deflection. This results in reduced aerodynamic drag and lower actuation effort. The optimized shapes were then used as targets to design a compliant structure capable of deforming as needed while remaining insensitive to external loads, with the overall actuation force minimized under additional dynamic performance requirements. Virtual testing of the complete device successfully validated its static and dynamic performance. The static validation, carried out in the presence of aerodynamic loads, confirmed the device's ability to reduce actuation forces under realistic operational conditions. The dynamic validation, conducted in dry conditions, demonstrated the potential of the system to reduce dynamic actuation loads. This implies the potential use of smaller and lighter motor actuators, thus improving the overall system efficiency.

1. Introduction

The increasing environmental and economic pressures in the aeronautical industry are driving research toward innovative solutions aimed at enhancing efficiency. Current investigations span multiple disciplines, including aerodynamics, propulsion, and structural design. Among the explored strategies, active flow control techniques have shown potential in suppressing flow separation, thereby improving aerodynamic performance [7]. Hybrid-electric propulsion systems represent a promising path for achieving sustainable aviation, as they can significantly reduce aircraft emissions [8]. Similarly, high-aspect-ratio wings are being studied for their ability to minimize lift-induced drag and improve fuel efficiency [9]. Another promising approach to increase the aerodynamic efficiency-to-weight ratio of aircraft is the integration of morphing devices. Morphing systems enable aircraft wings to adapt to various flight conditions, which can enhance overall mission performance and reduce fuel consumption [10]. While morphing technologies can be applied to high-lift systems [11–13], they also offer the potential to replace conventional control surfaces, such as hinged

ailerons, which typically introduce aerodynamic discontinuities and disturb laminar flow due to the presence of gaps. In particular, morphing ailerons have shown promise in meeting roll control requirements, even when constrained by limited chord extensions, as commonly found in high aspect ratio wings. Moreover, their functionality extends beyond roll moment increase: morphing trailing edges can also contribute effectively to maneuver load alleviation [14], offering a multi-functional solution within the broader context of next-generation wing design.

The design of a morphing aileron falls within the broader concept of variable camber wings, which aim to modify the airfoil curvature to increase lift while minimizing the associated drag increase [15–17]. Different kinds of skin structures can be employed to realize this concept. Segmented skins are based on the relative displacement or rotation of adjacent panels [18,19], while compliant skins exploit the elastic deformation of materials, typically using elastomers or fiber-reinforced composites [20]. Another approach involves flexible skins that take advantage of structural bending deformation, such as corrugated configurations [21,22].

* Corresponding author.

E-mail addresses: vittorio.cavalieri@polimi.it (V. Cavalieri), alessandro.degaspari@polimi.it (A. De Gaspari).

¹ PostDoctoral Researcher.

² Associate Professor.

Beyond the skin, morphing concepts require suitable internal structures to both enable shape adaptation and withstand aerodynamic loads. Lattice structures offer lightweight and stiff solutions for shape morphing applications [23,24]. Internal configurations based on initially curved beams can achieve large deformations while maintaining high load-bearing capacity [25]. Additionally, bistable composite laminates offer potential for energy-efficient morphing through their ability to maintain shape without continuous actuation [26]. In recent years, pioneering research is exploring the use of multi-stable panels to provide morphing capabilities to composite wings [27,28].

A promising approach for airfoil curvature adaptation is the Fish Bone Active Camber (FishBAC) concept, a bio-inspired design that mimics the flexible skeletal frame of a fish, with no mechanism or sliding skins [29]. Wind tunnel experiments have demonstrated that a continuous morphing trailing edge based on this concept can outperform traditional hinged flaps in terms of maximum lift-to-drag ratio [30].

Another morphing trailing edge concept is the Translation Induced Camber (TRIC), which allows for both chordwise and spanwise sliding of the bottom skin, using a combination of cross-sectional warping and skin bending to induce both camber and twist morphing [31]. The TRIC concept employs rotary actuators combined with linkages to apply a force to the bottom skin in the chordwise direction.

The most technologically mature trailing-edge device characterized by smooth curvature change is the Mission Adaptive Compliant Wing (MACW) flap, whose design was based on the distributed compliance concept. This technology was flight-tested to demonstrate extended laminar flow and reduced fuel consumption compared to conventional flaps. Moreover, it proved to be lighter and required lower actuation forces [32].

Compliant structures, leveraging elastic deformation instead of traditional mechanical linkages and hinges, are well-suited for airfoil camber control [33]. Their design typically involves specialized synthesis methods, often based on genetic algorithms combined with structural parameterizations, such as binary ground structure representation [34] or load path representation [35]. The latter has proven effective for both leading and trailing edge devices [1]. In this context, topology and sizing optimization are jointly addressed to satisfy both structural and kinematic requirements of morphing structures.

The design of a morphing device must account for the actuation system needed to realize shape changes. A promising strategy in this regard consists in coupling the actuation system with a sliding skin concept. In [1,2], a solution was introduced in which the sliding motion of the lower skin of a morphing trailing edge is combined with a compliant rib mechanism. Recently, a more general sliding-skins configuration has been proposed, merging the concept of a continuum parallel mechanism [36] either with a robotic system [37] or with an internal auxetic rib structure [38]. The approach adopted in the present work builds upon the first concept described above by introducing a new solution in which the actuation system is combined with the sliding motion of the lower skin only, while removing any internal ribs. The overall morphing structure is therefore optimized to simultaneously fulfill both the structural and kinematic requirements previously described, through the use of collaborative skins. This configuration further reduces weight and simplifies manufacturing, while the combination of a sliding lower skin with a fixed upper skin facilitates integration with wing box architectures and ensures structural continuity. In addition, it prevents any aerodynamic discontinuities, such as gaps or steps, on the upper surface of the airfoils, which would otherwise decrease aerodynamic efficiency. Finally, in this framework of integrated structural and actuator system optimization, minimizing actuation energy can be adopted as a design objective to ensure both lightweight and energy-efficient solutions [3,39].

Several advanced morphing demonstrators are currently being developed within the EU-funded HERWINGT project, supported by the Clean Aviation Joint Undertaking. The high-lift system installed on the

project's reference wing integrates a morphing droop nose and a morphing flap. The droop nose, developed by Politecnico di Milano (PoliMi), builds upon the structural architecture designed and validated in the Clean Sky 2 Airgreen 2 project, which culminated in the successful design and experimental testing of a full-scale demonstrator [4]. The flap, developed by CIRA, is a compliant morphing device obtained through topology optimization [40]. 2D aerodynamic analyses have shown that, in combination with flow control strategies to mitigate flow separation, the droop nose and the morphing flap together can achieve the required high-lift performance [41].

Additionally, the reference wing is equipped with morphing ailerons, whose design and validation are thoroughly discussed in this manuscript.

The proposed morphing aileron is designed to reduce aerodynamic drag during maneuvers while also minimizing the required actuation force. Compared to a traditional hinged aileron, drag reduction results from multiple factors. The morphing aileron is seamless, eliminating gaps that contribute to parasitic drag. Furthermore, it can achieve equivalent lift coefficient variations with smaller deflections than a hinged counterpart, further decreasing drag. Smaller deflections also reduce the aerodynamic work performed on the surface, which translates into lower actuation force requirements.

This combined reduction of aerodynamic drag and actuation demand represents another novelty of the present work. While the drag reduction improves aerodynamic efficiency, the lower actuation demand specifically enables the installation of more compact and lighter actuation systems, ultimately leading to overall weight savings. Moreover, the intrinsically simple design of the proposed device, together with the use of aeronautical materials and design requirements derived from a real aircraft, aims to replace conventional ailerons on actual wings, supporting acceptance by certification authorities.

The inherent structural flexibility of the morphing device enables further mass reduction compared to conventional hinged solutions, while also offering the potential to tailor the dynamic response of the system by accounting for dynamic properties during the design phase. Compliant structures have previously been employed as displacement amplification mechanisms in high-frequency active flow control systems [42]. Their use in dynamic applications can reduce peak power requirements, as demonstrated for a flapping-wing micro air vehicle [43]. However, morphing devices used in dynamic applications are typically limited to small-scale unmanned aerial vehicles, which face lower aerodynamic loads and actuation demands. Consequently, piezoelectric actuation is often used in such cases but is generally unsuitable for larger aircraft.

An additional novelty of the morphing aileron presented in this work is its high-bandwidth capability, which makes it suitable for installation on modern aircraft incorporating electromechanical actuators and advanced active control systems, including gust load alleviation and flutter suppression technologies. Thus, the flexibility of the structure not only reduces static actuation forces, but also allows for a reduction of dynamic actuation effort by designing the aileron as a dynamic resonant system, and tuning its first vibration mode to lie within or slightly above the target operational bandwidth. As a result, the required dynamic actuation force is minimized, and the static actuation forces become the dominant design driver for the actuation system.

This paper presents the optimal design and numerical validation of this morphing aileron. Section 2 introduces the reference wing, outlines the design requirements for the device, and describes the working principle of the actuation system conceived for the morphing concept. The overall design process, conducted at the full-scale level, is detailed in Sections 3 and 4, which cover the aerodynamic shape optimization and the structural optimization, respectively. Section 5 presents the functional and structural assessment performed using a high-fidelity finite element model, including virtual dry dynamic tests of the device. Finally, Section 6 summarizes the main findings of the work.

Fig. 1. Complete aircraft wing (left) and morphing aileron demonstrator mounted on outermost part of the wing for wind tunnel testing (right).

2. Morphing aileron: Configuration, requirements, and actuation concept

The reference configuration considered in this article is based on a high-aspect-ratio strut-braced wing, designed to enhance aerodynamic efficiency and reduce overall fuel consumption in a hybrid-electric regional aircraft. This architecture is adopted as the baseline for integrating the innovative morphing aileron device investigated in this work. The wing is equipped with three independent aileron devices with a total span of approximately five meters. An experimental demonstrator of this morphing device is currently under development for both dry and wind tunnel testing. Due to wind tunnel facility constraints, the demonstrator is limited to the outermost two meters of the aileron span. For this reason, the design of the outermost aileron device is of primary interest. Its root section, located two meters from the wing tip, approximately at the midpoint of the full-span aileron, is selected as the reference airfoil for aerodynamic evaluations and for the definition of the optimal morphing shape. The procedure developed for the shape optimization of this section is then applied to other airfoil locations along the span to reconstruct the complete 3D geometry of the morphing aileron. Fig. 1 shows the complete aircraft wing and the morphing aileron demonstrator attached to the wing box.

2.1. Design requirements

General design requirements for the morphing aileron include maintaining a continuous external shape, without steps or gaps, to preserve flow laminarity. Shape changes must be achieved through structural deformation, and therefore the skin is flexible and bends to match the desired geometry, while resisting axial stretching. The lower skin is allowed to slide along the tangential direction of the airfoil surface to accommodate the deformation. The deformable portion of the aileron begins at 70% of the chord, just aft of the rear spar located at 60%. This configuration ensures sufficient room for integrating the actuation kinematics.

The morphing aileron is designed to minimize the required actuation force and to achieve a dynamic bandwidth of up to 10 Hz, depending on the interaction with the selected electro-mechanical actuators (EMAs).

Simultaneously, the morphing aileron is also designed to match or improve the aerodynamic performance of the conventional hinged aileron. In particular, it must provide equivalent increments in lift coefficient across a range of flight conditions, ensuring at least the same roll control authority, alongside drag minimization and reduced structural weight. A reference deflection of $\pm 30^\circ$ is adopted based on the conventional aileron deflection at design maneuvering speed, V_A , corresponding to Mach 0.29 at sea level. In these conditions, the conventional solution exhibits significant flow separation, as illustrated in Fig. 2. The results correspond to a 2° angle of attack in the aircraft reference system, with the airfoil geometry including a local wing twist of 0.9° .

Both the minimization of the aerodynamic drag and the minimization of the actuation force are included as objectives from the early stage of the aero-structural shape optimization described in Section 3. The structural integrity of the morphing device, along with its ability to deform as desired, also complies with the design loads defined by CS-25 regulations, which are considered in Section 4.2 during the compliant structure optimization.

2.2. Morphing concept and actuation system

The morphing aileron architecture is shown in Fig. 3. The complete structure results from the optimization process described in Section 4. It consists of a compliant external skin with variable chordwise thickness, and an internal flexible spar connecting the upper and lower skins. The upper skin is clamped at 70% of the chord via ribs supporting the non-morphing region between the rear spar and the morphing device. In contrast, the lower skin is free to slide in the chord direction. At the same 70% chord location, it is connected to a stringer, which transfers the actuation force from the actuation mechanism to the skin and distributes this force along the span of the aileron, ensuring smooth deformation without introducing anticlastic distortion. The sliding motion of the lower skin occurs along the direction tangent to the airfoil at the attachment point. By applying pull or push forces to the lower skin through this mechanism, the entire structure bends to generate downward or upward deflected shapes, respectively.

The actuation system consists of multiple linear motors installed inside the wing-box and attached to the rear spar through an interface plate. At both ends of each motor shaft, a pair of linear guides allows the spanwise movement. Each end of the motor shaft is linked, through a rod, to a linear guide, installed on the ribs, that allow motion along the chordwise direction. The described mechanism converts the spanwise motion of the motor shaft into a controlled chordwise displacement of the lower skin, through the above mentioned stringer connection. The use of linear guides ensures low-friction motion while simultaneously supporting aerodynamic loads acting on the skin. The actuation layout is scalable and modular, making it suitable for implementation across the full span of the morphing device.

The proposed kinematic solution was identified as optimal for the 2-meter-span ailerons of the reference wing described in Section 2. Specifically, the spanwise actuation system adopted in this work requires a lower force for upward deflection and a similar force for downward deflection, compared to a morphing solution based on a chordwise actuation force applied to the skin.

Nevertheless, this configuration may not be suitable for larger ailerons or when trailing-edge twist is also required, as in the system described in [31]. In such scenarios, the morphing aileron structure proposed in this work could still be employed, but would need to be coupled with a different type of actuation.

Fig. 2. CFD results for the conventional hinged aileron at 2° angle of attack: downward deflection of 30° (left) and upward deflection of -30° (right). Flow is visualized in terms of streamlines and momentum along the chordwise direction.

Fig. 3. Morphing aileron configuration. The reference (undeflected) configuration is shown in beige; downward and upward deflected shapes are shown in blue. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

3. Aero-structural shape optimization

The focus of this section is the first level of the overall design process, which involves the aero-structural shape optimization of the morphing aileron. The objective of this phase is to identify feasible morphing shapes capable of achieving the required aerodynamic performance with minimal actuation effort. This is achieved through a parameterized shape description, aerodynamic simulations, and structural feasibility constraints. The resulting optimal shapes will be used as inputs for the subsequent structural optimization stage, which represents the second level of the overall design process.

3.1. Parameterization method

Shape optimization is performed using a parameterization technique that enables shape variation through a limited set of design variables. The original Class/Shape function Transformation (CST) method, proposed by Kulfan [44], has been extended by PoliMi [5] to identify the initial wing shape and to introduce the perturbations associated with morphing.

Once the geometries of both the original and the morphing wing surfaces are defined, the CST approach provides an analytical description of each configuration. The comparison between the two allows for the fully analytical computation of axial and bending strains in the skin by evaluating length variation ΔL and curvature variation $\Delta \kappa$, respectively. The curvature difference function can be also used to estimate

the resulting bending stress, assuming suitable values for skin thickness and Young's modulus, according to Kirchhoff plate theory [45].

This analytical framework also supports the estimation of actuation energy required for morphing. The estimate includes the strain energy required to deform the skin, still calculated analytically, and the aerodynamic work, partially analytical, associated with the skin displacement induced by the morphing deformation [3]. The actuation energy thus depends solely on the skin's bending strain, thickness, Young modulus, and the pressure distributions before and after morphing. It does not depend on a specific actuator configuration and can be evaluated independently in this phase.

Assuming a linear relationship between force and stroke applied to the lower skin, the estimated actuation energy allows computing the force to be applied to the lower skin to achieve the desired stroke. The corresponding stroke is directly evaluated by comparing the original and morphing wing surfaces through the CST analytical approach. It is important to note that this force does not directly represent the actuator load, which depends on actuator placement and kinematic configuration to be defined in later design phases.

3.2. Formulation of the optimization problem

The optimization aims to minimize both the aerodynamic drag coefficient C_d and the force required by the lower skin F_{skin} that, as explained above, provides an effective preliminary indicator of the actuation effort. The corresponding multi-objective optimization problem for

Fig. 4. Design variables defining the structural shape change of the morphing aileron.

Fig. 5. Response surfaces of the shape optimization objectives for the downward-deflected morphing aileron.

defining optimal morphing shapes is stated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned}
 & \min_{\mathbf{x}=\{\delta_{TE}; \Delta\beta\}} \{C_d(\mathbf{x}); F_{skin}(\mathbf{x})\} \\
 & \text{such that } C_l(\mathbf{x}) \geq |C_{l, Hinged}| \\
 & \Delta\psi_{wing-box} \equiv [0, 0.7] \\
 & |\Delta A(\mathbf{x})| \leq k_a \cdot A \\
 & |\Delta L_{UpperSkin}(\mathbf{x})| = 0 \\
 & |\Delta L_{LowerSkin}(\mathbf{x})| \leq k_c \cdot c \\
 & |\Delta\kappa(\mathbf{x})| \leq \overline{\Delta\kappa} \\
 & \mathbf{x}_{lb} \leq \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{x}_{ub}
 \end{aligned} \tag{1}$$

Here, the design variables $\mathbf{x} = \{\delta_{TE}; \Delta\beta\}$ represent the trailing-edge equivalent rotation and the boat-tail angle variation of the airfoil, respectively. They are constrained to vary within the lower and upper bounds \mathbf{x}_{lb} and \mathbf{x}_{ub} , respectively. The design variables are represented in Fig. 4. The vertex of the equivalent rotation angle is located at the center of the circle tangent to both the upper and lower surfaces where the morphing deformation begins. The two design variables govern a total of four shape parameters, two on the upper surface and two on the lower surface, and these parameters enable the description of all feasible shape variations in the trailing-edge region [5].

The problem formulation includes structural, and aerodynamic constraints. The first constraint ensures that the lift coefficient C_l is at least equal to that of the fully deflected hinged aileron ($C_{l, Hinged}$), evaluated at the design maneuvering speed (V_A) condition at 2° angle of attack depicted in Fig. 2. The lift coefficient values for the hinged solutions are 1.5605 and -0.7936 for downward and upward deflections, respectively. The enforcement of this trim condition, combined with the drag minimization, corresponds to maximize the aerodynamic efficiency in the same condition. The second constraint imposes that shape changes do not affect the region within the wing box, defined for $\psi \in [0, 0.7]$ of the chord [5]. The remaining structural constraints guarantee feasible morphing behavior:

- maximum internal area change ΔA limited to $k_a = 5\%$,
- zero axial strain in the upper skin,
- maximum lower skin stroke limited to $k_c = 2.5\%$ of the chord $c = 1.856$ m,
- maximum curvature variation $\Delta\kappa$ limited to $\overline{\Delta\kappa} = 18$.

The optimization process is conducted using a Design of Experiments (DOE) approach. Aerodynamic, structural, and actuation results are approximated via response surfaces, built using a Latin hypercube sampling of 40 points in the design space. Each shape is defined analytically using CST, and aerodynamic analyses are performed using the open-source Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) based CFD solver SU2 [46].

The response surfaces of the objective functions for the downward deflection case, characterized by higher values of drag and required skin force, are presented in Fig. 5.

3.3. Optimization results

The solution of the multi-objective problem yields a Pareto front representing the trade-off between drag and required lower skin force. Fig. 6 illustrates the Pareto fronts for downward and upward deflections. Three candidate solutions are highlighted for each deflection case. Their corresponding morphing shapes are shown in Fig. 7.

Among the candidate shapes, the final choice was made by prioritizing the minimization of required skin force, while still ensuring competitive aerodynamic performance. Indeed, all the solutions on the Pareto front achieve a drag reduction compared to the conventional hinged aileron, and the additional gain achievable by moving toward the left side of the Pareto front is marginal. Therefore, prioritizing an actuation force reduction is more beneficial, as it allows for the use of smaller and lighter actuators. The selected downward and upward deflection shapes, highlighted in red in the Pareto fronts, are characterized by the optimal variables $(\delta_{TE}, \Delta\beta) = (14^\circ, 25^\circ)$ and $(\delta_{TE}, \Delta\beta) = (-15^\circ, -27^\circ)$, and corresponding lower skin strokes of -35.5 mm and 37.9 mm, respectively. These stroke values satisfy the constraints and are used as input for the

Fig. 6. Pareto fronts of the shape optimization problem for downward (left) and upward (right) deflections.

Fig. 7. Highlighted morphing shapes selected from the Pareto fronts for downward (left) and upward (right) deflections.

Fig. 8. CFD results at 2° AoA: momentum along the chord and streamlines for 14° downward (left) and -15° upward (right) equivalent deflection of the morphing aileron.

subsequent structural optimization and model validation phases. The optimal values of drag coefficient for the selected downward and upward deflections are $C_{d,down} = 0.02763$ and $C_{d,up} = 0.01126$, while the corresponding values of aerodynamic efficiency are $E_{down} = 56.5$ and $E_{up} = -70.5$.

Fig. 8 compares the aerodynamic flowfields of the selected morphing shapes at the design maneuvering speed. Compared to the results for the hinged aileron (Fig. 2), the morphing shapes exhibit significantly reduced separation and boundary layer detachment. In the following section, a comparison between the aerodynamic behavior of the morphing aileron and the hinged aileron will also be presented, focusing on aerodynamic coefficients, pressure distribution, and actuation loads. This comparison will be based on the actual deformation of the optimized compliant structure, rather than the shape variations prescribed by the CST parameterization.

4. Compliant structure optimization

The design of the compliant structure is achieved through a combined topology and sizing optimization process. Once actuated, the structure must be capable of producing external shapes that closely approximate the target configurations obtained from the aerodynamic shape optimization described in the previous section. The overall structural layout consists of an internal support structure connected to a variable-thickness skin. The behavior of the device is governed both by the topology of the internal structure and by the thickness distribution of the skin. The internal structure supports the skin in sustaining loads and plays a crucial role in achieving the desired deformation. In this concept, the actuation system is connected directly to the skin and drives its sliding motion, as described in Section 2.2.

Fig. 9. Finite element model and optimization variables for the structural design of the morphing aileron.

4.1. Design optimization methodology

The design approach adopted in this study is specifically tailored for trailing-edge devices. It assumes a simplified structural configuration compared to a full load path representation, omitting internal points. As a result, the internal structure is composed of elements that directly connect the upper and lower skins. This choice offers two primary advantages: it reduces architectural complexity, thus simplifying manufacturing and lowering stress levels compared to the load path configurations used in leading-edge devices [6], and it reduces the number of design variables, as no internal point coordinates are included. An illustrative finite element model of the morphing aileron and its optimization variables is shown in Fig. 9.

The finite element (FE) model is developed using Abaqus software, selected for its advanced nonlinear analysis capabilities. The structure is modeled using 4-node quadrilateral shell elements with a finite-strain formulation, both for the skin and the internal structure. A surface-to-surface tie constraint is employed to model the connection between the skin and internal structure. The model represents a spanwise section of the device, thus excluding 3D effects which will be addressed at a later stage in the design process. The internal structure spans the entire section and represents compliant spars.

Boundary conditions are used to model the interface between the skin and the wing. The upper skin is clamped, while the lower skin is free to slide along a direction tangent to the airfoil surface at the point where morphing deformation begins. In the reference configuration, the lower skin is clamped and the actuator is locked. During actuation, the prescribed displacement at the lower skin is enforced. This stroke is determined from the CST-based geometric description, corresponding to the length variation of the lower skin.

The design variables for the optimization problem, illustrated in Fig. 9, are:

- **Beam sizes** (real variables): in-plane dimensions of the internal structural elements.
- **Boundary sizes** (real variables): thicknesses of the boundary segments into which the skin is partitioned.
- **Boundary arclength** (real variables): non-dimensional arclength positions on the upper and lower skins where internal beams may be connected.
- **Beam destination** (integer variables): integer variables indicating which destination points the internal beams are connected to.

- **Beam existence** (binary variables): used to activate or deactivate internal beams.

The simplicity of this approach, compared to the complete load path representation method [47], lies in the non-use of internal points. As a result, load paths connect only output points, simplifying the connectivity definition. Each load path is fully defined by two attachment points, and its presence or absence is governed by a binary variable (1 or 0), without requiring filtering techniques. The topology is thus controlled by the combined use of the boundary arclength, beam destination, and beam existence variables. In parallel, the use of beam and boundary size variables addresses the sizing problem. Using arclength-based positions as design variables offers significant advantages. A single scalar value suffices to define a point along the skin, whose coordinates can be reconstructed through the CST. Furthermore, since these arclength positions are continuous variables, the formulation is inherently mesh-independent.

4.2. Optimization problem and results

The primary goal of the morphing device is to achieve the optimal shapes required for the desired aerodynamic performance. However, being an aeronautical component, the device must also satisfy structural requirements under each considered load condition. Specifically, the structure must withstand aerodynamic loads without significant deformation, regardless of whether the configuration is morphing or not. Additionally, the structure must comply with typical strength verifications in terms of allowable stress.

The attempt to achieve the target shapes resulting from shape optimization is formalized as the minimization of the least-square error (LSE) between the deformed shape, obtained via finite element analysis under actuation, and the desired target shape. The minimization of LSE, evaluated at a set of skin control points, represents the kinematic requirement associated with morphing.

On the other hand, the structural requirement related to load-bearing capacity can be formulated as the minimization of the strain energy, assuming a fixed lower skin. Alternatively, the required stiffness can be promoted by minimizing the displacements at the skin control points, which can be formalized as the minimization of the LSE between the deformed shape under aerodynamic loads and the undeformed, unloaded configuration.

The selected objective functions for this optimization problem are:

- Minimization of the kinematic LSE in both downward and upward deflection configurations, under the corresponding aerodynamic loads (Mach = 0.29, h = 0 m; AoA = 8deg for downward deflection and AoA = -4deg for upward deflection), when the mechanism is actuated.
- Minimization of the structural LSE to preserve the undeformed airfoil shape, under aerodynamic loads corresponding to the most critical flight condition (Mach = 0.45, h = 0 m, AoA = 4°), when the mechanism is not actuated.

A lower constraint is imposed on the frequency of the first vibration mode f_1 to ensure a dynamic behavior compatible with a 10 Hz actuation bandwidth. This prevents the device from acting as a low-pass filter, which could delay the control response. The natural frequency is computed assuming boundary conditions that allow the lower skin to slide freely, thereby promoting the design of a dynamic resonant system capable of following fast control commands.

The objective and constraint functions are evaluated through nonlinear finite element analyses in Abaqus. Constraints on maximum strain are not included in the optimization, as CST-based estimates indicate that the strain levels required to achieve the target curvature changes are non-critical. Therefore, strains are verified only for the final optimal solution.

The optimization problem for the definition of the optimal structure is formulated as:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{x}} \quad & LSE_i(\mathbf{x}), \quad i = 1, 2, 3 \\ & \mathbf{r}_i(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{0}, \quad i = 1, 2, 3 \\ & f_1 \geq \bar{f} \\ & \mathbf{x}_{lb} \leq \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{x}_{ub} \end{aligned} \quad (2)$$

where the design variables \mathbf{x} define the topology and sizing of the structure. The objective functions correspond to the LSE values for the three configurations: downward and upward deflections (kinematic requirements) and undeformed configuration (structural requirement). The residual equations $\mathbf{r}_i(\mathbf{x}) = 0$ ensure equilibrium in the nonlinear analyses. The constraint on the first mode frequency f_1 guarantees compliance with the bandwidth requirement, with $\bar{f} = 10$ Hz.

The multi-objective nature of the problem makes it suitable for a multi-point design optimization strategy, seeking a trade-off between the different deflected shapes associated with different flight conditions. The aerodynamic loads for the selected configurations are obtained from 2D CFD simulations of CST-defined target shapes. In the finite element model, these loads are applied as pressure distributions on the skin, and remain normal to the deformed surface throughout the morphing process. The undeformed shape pressure field is applied at the start of the analysis, and the pressures are linearly increased until they match those associated with the final target shape. When the deformed shape obtained by optimization converges to the target shape, the applied aerodynamic loads can be considered accurate. The boundary conditions used to enforce lower skin motion correspond to the length variations derived from the CST evaluation, as described in Section 3.3.

The reaction force required to enforce the skin motion represents the actuation force needed to achieve the desired shape under aerodynamic loads. Although actuation force is not explicitly minimized in this multi-objective problem, the formulation, based on tracking target shapes defined by the optimization problem of Eq. (1), implicitly favors designs that lead to lower actuation loads. Moreover, for a given optimal shape, the actuation force depends on the local thickness distribution, which will be further refined through a local optimization step aiming to reduce force while preserving shape quality, as defined later in Eq. (3).

The multi-objective problem is solved using a controlled, elitist genetic algorithm, which promotes both high-fitness individuals and those that contribute to population diversity. Parent selection is performed through binary tournament selection: each parent is chosen as the best of two randomly selected candidates. Genetic diversity is introduced

through crossover and mutation operators, which are designed to handle both continuous, discrete and binary design variables. For size-related variables, crossover exchanges variables of the same type (boundary or beam) between parents with a certain probability, while mutation replaces a variable with a randomly selected value within bounds. For topology-related variables, crossover may exchange beams between parents, and mutation may alter a beam's destination or toggle its presence in the model. Structural integrity rules are enforced to prevent overlapping or intersecting beams, although beams may share common end points on the skins.

The initial population is randomly generated within the allowed design space. Boundary arclength variables are selected partly at random and partly from a predefined set of optimal active points on the skin. This set is derived from the union of active points identified for each morphing shape and correspond to locations that allow to better fit curvature difference between morphing and undeformed shapes, identified through a dedicated minimization process [1].

The genetic algorithm returns a Pareto set of optimal solutions. Among these, a final design is selected for further refinement. In this second step, a local optimization using a sequential quadratic programming algorithm adjusts the skin thickness distribution to reduce actuation force while preserving the achieved shape. The corresponding problem is:

$$\begin{aligned} \min_{\mathbf{x}} \quad & \max_i |F_i(\mathbf{x})|, \quad i = 1, 2 \\ & LSE_i(\mathbf{x}) \leq \overline{LSE}_i, \quad i = 1, 2, 3 \\ & \mathbf{r}_i(\mathbf{x}) = \mathbf{0}, \quad i = 1, 2, 3 \\ & f_1 \geq \bar{f} \\ & \mathbf{x}_{lb} \leq \mathbf{x} \leq \mathbf{x}_{ub} \end{aligned} \quad (3)$$

The objective is to minimize the peak force required on the lower skin for both downward or upward deflection cases, which allows for smaller actuators and contributes to mass savings. The LSE constraints ensure that shape quality is not degraded from the global optimization results. Other constraints remain unchanged from Eq. (2). In this sizing optimization, the topology (including internal spar placement) is kept fixed.

The structural configuration of the final optimal design is shown in Fig. 10, together with the deformed shapes and corresponding maximum principal strain contours. Shape quality comparisons are provided in Fig. 11.

A modal analysis of the final optimized design is conducted for two different boundary conditions: with sliding and fixed lower skin. The corresponding first-mode frequencies are 10.9 Hz and 51.5 Hz, respectively. The former satisfies the minimum dynamic constraint included in the optimization, while the latter ensures that the actuation command remains in phase with the structural response within the bandwidth of interest, as further discussed in Section 5.2.

4.3. Comparison between morphing and hinged aileron

The aerodynamic advantage of the morphing aileron over a conventional hinged solution is demonstrated by comparing their aerodynamic performance at the design maneuvering speed. Fig. 12 shows the lift coefficient and the efficiency as functions of the angle of attack, while Fig. 13 represents the polar curves. The $C_l - \alpha$ curves shows that the constraint on the lift coefficient is satisfied, since for positive deflection morphing C_l is higher than the hinged one, whereas they are equal for negative deflections. The morphing configurations exhibit significantly lower drag, nearly an order of magnitude less in the case of downward deflection, while achieving the same variations in lift coefficient as the hinged configurations. This results in a clear improvement in aerodynamic efficiency, as shown in the graph at the bottom of Fig. 12, where the 14° downward morphing configuration is compared with the 30° hinged configuration, and the -15° upward morphing configuration is

Fig. 10. Optimal solution from the structural optimization problem (in gray) and downward/upward deformed shapes with contours of maximum principal strain.

Fig. 11. Comparison between deformed and target shapes for downward (left) and upward (right) deflection.

compared with the -30° hinged configuration. The efficiency difference between the morphing and hinged solutions is highlighted across the full range of angles of attack.

Validation of the morphing aileron also includes the aerodynamic analysis of the deformed shapes obtained from the finite element simulations, to verify that the lift coefficient requirements are met by the actual structural solution. To this end, CFD analyses are performed and the results are compared with those of the corresponding target shapes. This comparison, carried out at the same design conditions used for the structural optimization described in Section 4.2, shows minor differences in lift and drag coefficients, leading to an efficiency reduction of about 1% of the deformed shape compared to the target. Nonetheless, the aerodynamic efficiency of the deformed shape remains about three times higher than that of the hinged aileron (2.8 and 3.3 for downward and upward deflections, respectively). In Fig. 14, the pressure coefficient distributions of the deformed and target shapes are compared, alongside the distribution for the hinged aileron.

Once the aerodynamic performance of the designed morphing solution has been validated, an actuation force comparison with the corresponding hinged solution can also be performed. The total actuation force required for the morphing aileron consists of two contributions: a structural component needed to deform the structure, and an aerodynamic component needed to counteract the aerodynamic loads. This total force is obtained through finite element analyses of the optimized structure under aerodynamic loads. The structural contribution is estimated as the force required to achieve the morphing deformation in the absence of aerodynamic loads. The aerodynamic contribution is then computed as the difference between the total force and this structural component.

In contrast, for the conventional hinged aileron, the actuation force is entirely due to aerodynamic loads. It is estimated based on the hinge moment of a rigidly rotated aileron, assuming an internal actuation mechanism, as external modifications of the aerodynamic surfaces are not permitted on the reference wing.

Fig. 12. Comparison of aerodynamic performance between morphing and hinged ailerons: lift coefficient and efficiency versus angle of attack.

Fig. 13. Comparison between morphing and hinged aileron in terms of polar curves.

Fig. 14. Comparison of pressure coefficient distributions between morphing and hinged aileron.

The comparison between the hinged and morphing aileron solutions at maximum deflection and maneuvering speed is presented on the left in Fig. 15, where absolute values of the forces, normalized over a 1-meter span, are shown. Note that downward and upward deflections require forces of opposite signs, corresponding to pulling and pushing actions on the lower skin, respectively.

Although the morphing solution requires additional structural energy, especially in the upward deflection case, the total actuation force remains lower than that of the hinged configuration. In the case of downward deflection, the force is reduced by approximately 30%. This is due to the morphing aileron's ability to generate the required lift coefficient with a smaller effective trailing-edge rotation compared to the rigid deflection of the hinged aileron.

As a result, the designed morphing aileron outperforms the traditional hinged aileron in terms of both aerodynamic performance and actuation force requirements, as summarized on the right in Fig. 15. The design process has successfully led to a morphing aileron capable of improving aerodynamic efficiency while reducing deployment effort, thanks to the multiple degrees of freedom involved in the shape adaptation.

5. Numerical assessment of the morphing aileron device

The previous sections have detailed the optimal design of the aerodynamic shape and the subsequent structural configuration for the airfoil section located 2 m from the tip. Shape optimization is then extended to additional sections along the aileron span to achieve a nearly con-

stant deflection across the span. The resulting three-dimensional optimal morphing shapes corresponding to maximum downward and upward deflections are depicted in Fig. 16.

These optimized shapes were provided to Leonardo for aircraft-level CFD RANS simulations aimed at assessing the aerodynamic benefits of the morphing aileron. In addition, the resulting surface pressure distributions have been used to derive the three-dimensional aerodynamic loads for the structural verification described in the following section. Fig. 16 also shows the pressure coefficient distributions for two representative design conditions at maneuvering speed.

Starting from the optimal structural solution described in Section 4, the design is propagated along the span of the aileron. A high-fidelity 3D model is developed in *Abaqus* to assess the structural integrity of the device under both actuation and aerodynamic loads. Actuation is introduced directly in the lower skin as an enforced displacement (stroke), while pressure loads are derived from the 3D CFD pressure coefficient distributions for different design points within the aircraft's load envelope.

This assessment is conducted on a two-meter span model representing the outer portion of the aileron, using the final sizing previously identified. In particular, the optimized thicknesses are directly applied to the section from 2 m to 1 m from the tip, while a scaling factor of 0.92 is applied to the outermost section. This scaling factor was selected to keep the force required for a unit stroke of the lower skin constant along the span, while preserving structural strength without over-sizing the outermost region.

The finite element model, shown in Fig. 17, includes shell elements for both the skin and the internal compliant spar. The upper skin is clamped at 70% of the chord, representing the transition to the non-morphing part of the wing. The lower skin, also at 70% chord, remains free to slide except at four actuation input points, where enforced-motion boundary conditions are applied. These displacement values are consistent with those derived from CST-based shape calculations and are prescribed at the end sections; intermediate values are obtained via linear interpolation along the span.

The motion is transferred to the skin using *Abaqus* distributing coupling constraints: the nodes of the skin are made dependent on the translational and rotational motion of a reference node located at each actuation point. Additionally, a stringer is integrated on the lower skin as a local reinforcement to provide adequate spanwise stiffness and ensure structural response under aerodynamic loads.

5.1. Structural and shape verification

The developed model is used to verify the three-dimensional behavior of the device in terms of both structural feasibility and shape quality. Nonlinear finite element analyses are performed by enforcing motion at the actuation input points and applying aerodynamic pressure loads on the external surface. These simulations are carried out for relevant design load cases corresponding to maneuvering speed, dive speed, and maximum operating speed, for both downward and upward deflection configurations.

The results obtained under ultimate loads at V_A for the two maximum deflection cases are shown in Fig. 18, which includes the distribution of maximum principal strains and the Tsai-Hill failure index. The strain levels within the morphing aileron structure at maximum deflection remain well below the tensile strain limit of the adopted material.

A composite material made of S glass-fiber fabric and epoxy resin is selected for the compliant structure. The material properties are listed in Table 1. This same material was previously adopted for the manufacturing of a droop nose prototype, successfully tested during a former project, proving its suitability for morphing applications [4].

The maximum Tsai-Hill failure index, equal to 0.32, is obtained for the downward deflected configuration under ultimate load at V_A with $AoA = 15\text{deg}$. The corresponding margin of safety is 2.1, confirming that the structural strength requirements are satisfied. Further reduction of

Fig. 15. Force comparison with contributions to total force (left) and comparison of aerodynamic and actuation performances between hinged and morphing aileron (right).

Fig. 16. Surface CAD model of the reference wing equipped with the morphing aileron and pressure coefficient from 3D CFD computations at maximum deflections: downward deflection at AoA = 15° (left) and upward deflection at AoA = -4° (right).

Fig. 17. 3D finite element model of the morphing aileron for structural verification.

Fig. 18. Structural verification for the morphing aileron: maximum principal strain (left) and Tsai-Hill failure index (right).

Table 1
Material properties of the glass-fiber fabric EE302S ER450 38 %.

Parameter	Value
0° Tensile modulus	28.4 GPa
90° Tensile modulus	27.2 GPa
Poisson's ratio	0.16
In Plane Shear modulus	3.98 GPa
0° Tensile strength	687 MPa
0° Compressive strength	540 MPa
90° Tensile strength	580 MPa
90° Compressive strength	505 MPa
In Plane Shear strength	97.5 MPa
Elongation at failure	3.05 %
Cured Ply Thickness	0.271 mm

Fig. 19. First buckling shape ($\lambda = 14$) for the morphing aileron structure.

this margin to decrease weight is not feasible, as the design is primarily governed by stiffness constraints related to the kinematic and structural performance required for morphing.

A linear buckling analysis is carried out to evaluate the buckling resistance of the designed structure. Starting from the undeformed configuration with fixed actuation points, and applying aerodynamic pressure loads corresponding to the dive speed condition, a buckling safety margin of 13 is obtained. This result confirms that the adopted thickness distribution and internal spar configuration provide sufficient stiffness to avoid buckling as a critical design condition. The deformation shape of the first buckling mode is shown in Fig. 19.

Modal analyses are also performed to assess the dynamic behavior. In the configuration with fixed actuation points, the first vibration mode (shown on the left in Fig. 20) has a frequency of 56.5 Hz. This value is sufficiently high to reasonably exclude any dynamic coupling with the target actuation bandwidth of 10 Hz. Additional modal analyses are carried out with the lower skin free to slide. The first mode shape, shown on the right in Fig. 20, has a frequency of 12.6 Hz, which still complies with the 10 Hz requirement.

Regarding shape quality, the deformed surfaces exhibit a smooth profile, free from local waviness, and display minimal deviation from the target shapes defined during the first design level. This confirms that the device, when applied to a finite-span configuration and accounting for the actual tapering in the outer wing region, is able to reproduce the optimized CST-defined three-dimensional shapes. Additionally, the effect of aerodynamic loads on the external shape is found to be very limited. A comparison between the finite element deformed shapes and

the target geometries is shown in Fig. 21, considering limit loads at maneuvering speed.

Since the motion of the input points is enforced in the static analyses, the corresponding reaction forces in the sliding direction are available as reference data for the actuation system design, which lies beyond the scope of this study. Fig. 22 reports the total internal force in the lower skin section located 1.5 m from the tip as a function of skin displacement, for two flight conditions. Positive values of force and displacement correspond to upward deflection. The results are consistent with those obtained at the 2D level in Fig. 15. Both structural and aerodynamic contributions to the total actuation force are shown: the structural contribution is computed without aerodynamic loads, while the aerodynamic contribution is obtained as the difference between the total and the structural components.

5.2. Virtual dynamic tests

The dynamic performance of the morphing aileron structure is assessed through modal and transient dynamic analyses performed on the finite element model. The modal analysis presented in the previous section, which considers the sliding lower skin, is here extended by including the effect of the actuation system mass. The added inertia reduces the natural frequency of the structure in the *free commands* configuration.

At this stage of the project, a dedicated aeronautical actuator for full-scale application is not yet available. Therefore, the actuator mass is estimated as the value required to achieve a first mode frequency of 10 Hz with a sliding lower skin. A total mass of 6.4 kg is considered. However, higher masses would not necessarily prevent the achievement of the target bandwidth, as discussed in the following.

The finite element model including the actuation system, shown in Fig. 23, is used to perform non-linear dynamic analyses using implicit direct integration, with the aim of investigating the transient response of the system. In particular, a displacement-controlled analysis is performed by imposing a sinusoidal stroke of 20 mm amplitude. A frequency sweep input is applied over a duration of 24 s, varying linearly from 0 to 12 Hz.

These analyses are carried out without considering aerodynamic loads, as they aim to reproduce the laboratory dry tests planned for the demonstrator prior to wind tunnel testing. The aeroelastic behavior will then be experimentally assessed in a dedicated wind tunnel campaign.

Fig. 24 shows the time history of the imposed stroke along with the corresponding actuation force required to follow the command. The force amplitude initially decreases and reaches a minimum at approximately $t = 20$ s, after which it increases again towards the end of the simulation.

A detailed view of the time history reveals that, during the initial phase, the stroke and force are in phase, as shown on the left in Fig. 25. After $t = 20$ s, a 180° phase shift occurs, resulting in an out-of-phase response, as illustrated on the right. Nonetheless, throughout the entire simulation, the actuator stroke and the vertical displacement of the trailing edge remain in phase. This confirms the absence of command inversion phenomena, owing to the fact that the structure remains dynamically faster than the actuation, as verified by the fixed-command first mode frequency of 56.5 Hz.

Fig. 20. First vibration mode with fixed (left) and sliding (right) lower skin.

Fig. 21. Comparison between 3D finite element deformed shapes and target shapes.

Fig. 22. Internal forces applied to the lower skin for two flight conditions at Mach 0.29: AoA = 15deg (left), AoA = -4deg (right).

Fig. 23. Finite element model of the morphing aileron including the actuation system.

Fig. 24. Time history of the actuation force obtained from the dynamic analysis with sweep command (from 0 Hz to 12 Hz) imposed to the actuator stroke.

Fig. 25. Details of the time history of stroke and actuation force: time intervals before anti-resonance (left) and after anti-resonance (right).

Fig. 26. Amplitude (left) and phase (right) of the transfer function between actuator stroke and actuation force.

The corresponding amplitude and phase of the transfer function between actuator stroke and force are reported in Fig. 26. The amplitude plot shows an anti-resonance peak at 10 Hz, whose magnitude would increase in the absence of the added actuation mass. Throughout the operational frequency range (0–10 Hz), dynamic actuation proves to be less demanding than static actuation, thanks to the compliant nature of the morphing structure. The phase plot shows the phase inversion

around the anti-resonance, confirming the trends observed in the time histories. The results are obtained for a configuration in which the first sliding mode frequency is tuned to 10 Hz. However, even lower natural frequencies in the range of 5–10 Hz would still ensure that the actuation force requirements remain below those of static actuation.

Once the physical demonstrator is built, the planned dry tests will provide further insight into the dynamic response of the system, partic-

ularly in terms of damping characterization, which cannot be reliably captured through numerical simulation. In the current analyses, a constant damping ratio $\xi = 0.05$ has been assumed.

6. Conclusion

This paper has presented the design and optimization of a morphing aileron device capable of outperforming a conventional hinged aileron in terms of aerodynamic efficiency and actuation requirements. The design workflow was based on a coupled aero-structural shape optimization with energy feedback, used to define the optimal upward and downward deflected shapes. A multi-objective topology and sizing optimization was then applied to generate the compliant structure capable of morphing, once actuated, to the target shapes previously defined. This was followed by a sizing refinement focused on minimizing the required actuation force. All design activities were conducted at full scale, targeting the outboard control surface of a reference wing for a hybrid-electric regional aircraft.

The optimized morphing aileron demonstrated multiple advantages over the conventional hinged solution. It achieved the same roll performance with a lower equivalent deflection angle, leading to a reduction in aerodynamic drag. From the actuation perspective, the device required lower force inputs, enabling both energy savings and the potential for smaller, lighter actuation systems.

Following the design optimization, structural and shape verification were performed using a high-fidelity finite element model. These assessments confirmed both the structural integrity of the compliant concept and the ability of the device to match the target shapes accurately, even considering the wing taper over the outermost two meters of span.

The dynamic response of the morphing system was also evaluated. The results confirmed that the compliant architecture, acting as a dynamic resonant system, allows the device to meet the 10 Hz bandwidth requirement without increasing the actuation force compared to static conditions. This behavior supports the feasibility of high-bandwidth operation at full scale, a feature typically limited to smaller air vehicles applications.

The presented work will continue with the manufacturing of a demonstrator of the morphing aileron, which will undergo both static and dynamic dry testing. The same high-fidelity structural model used for virtual dynamic assessments has also been employed to simulate these forthcoming laboratory dry tests. Future work will focus on the coupled simulation of this model with a CFD model of the reference wing, in order to capture the full aeroelastic behavior of the system, including the dynamic response and the evaluation of actuation loads in the presence of aerodynamic effects. These developments will be followed by wind tunnel testing for the final experimental validation of the proposed morphing concept.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Vittorio Cavalieri: Writing - original draft, Visualization, Validation, Software, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis; **Alessandro De Gaspari:** Writing - review & editing, Resources, Project administration, Software, Supervision, Methodology, Conceptualization.

Data availability

Data will be made available on request.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Acknowledgments

This project has received funding from the Clean Aviation Joint Undertaking under grant agreement No. 101102010. The granting authority receives support from the European Union's Horizon Europe research and innovation programme and the Clean Aviation Joint Undertaking members other than the Union. The authors would like to express their sincere gratitude to Prof. Sergio Ricci for making the start of this research possible.

References

- [1] A. De Gaspari, S. Ricci, A two-level approach for the optimal design of morphing wings based on compliant structures, *J. Intell. Mater. Syst. Struct.* 22 (10) (2011) 1091–1111. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1045389X11409081>
- [2] A. De Gaspari, L. Riccobene, S. Ricci, Design, manufacturing and wind tunnel validation of a morphing compliant wing, *J. Aircr.* 55 (6) (2018) 2313–2326. <https://doi.org/10.2514/1.C034860>
- [3] A. De Gaspari, Study on the actuation aspects for a morphing aileron using an energy-based design approach, *Actuators* 11 (7) (2022) 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.3390/act11070185>
- [4] A. De Gaspari, V. Cavalieri, S. Ricci, Experimental and performance validation of a full-scale morphing droop nose design based on composite compliant structures, *Compos. Struct.* 348 (118502) (2024) 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2024.118502>
- [5] A. De Gaspari, S. Ricci, Knowledge-based shape optimization of morphing wing for more efficient aircraft, *Int. J. Aerosp. Eng.* 2015, 325724 (2015) 1 – 19. <https://doi.org/10.1155/2015/325724>
- [6] V. Cavalieri, A. De Gaspari, S. Ricci, Optimization of compliant adaptive structures in the design of a morphing droop nose, *Smart Mater. Struct.* 29 (7) (2020) 22. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-665X/ab8902>
- [7] Q. Sun, F. Bahri, M. Jabbar, W. Stryczniwicz, R. Jefferson-Loveday, B. Stefes, A. Büscher, Suppression of flow separation of a high-lift wing with active flow control, *Aerosp. Sci. Technol.* 159 (2025) 110017. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2025.110017>
- [8] K. Abu Salem, G. Palaia, A. A. Quarta, Review of hybrid-electric aircraft technologies and designs: critical analysis and novel solutions, *Prog. Aerosp. Sci.* 141 (2023) 100924. Special Issue on Green Aviation. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paerosci.2023.100924>
- [9] Y. Ma, A. Elham, Designing high aspect ratio wings: a review of concepts and approaches, *Prog. Aerosp. Sci.* 145 (2024) 100983. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.paerosci.2024.100983>
- [10] D. A. Burdette, J. R. R. A. Martins, Design of a transonic wing with an adaptive morphing trailing edge via aerostructural optimization, *Aerosp. Sci. Technol.* 81 (2018) 192–203. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2018.08.004>
- [11] A. Rudenko, A. Hannig, H. P. Monner, P. Horst, Extremely deformable morphing leading edge: optimization, design and structural testing, *J. Intell. Mater. Syst. Struct.* 29 (5) (2018) 764–773. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1045389X17721036>
- [12] C. Contell Asins, V. Landersheim, J.-D. Wacker, S. Adachi, S. Arnold-Keifer, M. May, Design of a morphing leading edge as a high lift device for a regional aircraft, *IOP Conf. Ser. Mater. Sci. Eng.* 1024 (1) (2021) 012033. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1757-899X/1024/1/012033>
- [13] A. Marouf, D. Charbonnier, J. B. Vos, R. El Akoury, Y. Hoarou, M. Braza, Morphing of high-lift wing-flap system with cambering and trailing-edge flapping at high Reynolds number towards a full airplane application, *J. Fluids Struct.* 127 (2024) 104111. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jfluidstructs.2024.104111>
- [14] Y. Wu, J. Li, Y. Dai, Y. Li, C. Yang, Active maneuver load alleviation for a pitching wing via spanwise-distributed camber morphing, *Aerosp. Sci. Technol.* 155 (2024) 109693. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2024.109693>
- [15] K. Bonnema, S. Smith, AFTI/F-111 mission adaptive wing flight research program, in: 4th Flight Test Conference, 1988, p. 2118. <https://doi.org/10.2514/6.1988-2118>
- [16] J. Szodrach, R. Hilbig, Variable wing camber for transport aircraft, *Prog. Aerosp. Sci.* 25 (3) (1988) 297–328. [https://doi.org/10.1016/0376-0421\(88\)90003-6](https://doi.org/10.1016/0376-0421(88)90003-6)
- [17] H. P. Monner, Realization of an optimized wing camber by using formvariable flap structures, *Aerosp. Sci. Technol.* 5 (7) (2001) 445–455. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S1270-9638\(01\)01118-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S1270-9638(01)01118-X)
- [18] R. Pecora, Morphing wing flaps for large civil aircraft: evolution of a smart technology across the clean sky program, *Chin. J. Aeronaut.* 34 (7) (2021) 13–28. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.cja.2020.08.004>
- [19] A. Yu, F. J. Xi, A. Moosavian, B. Li, Design of a sliding morphing skin with segmented rigid panels, *J. Aircr.* 55 (5) (2018) 1985–1994. <https://doi.org/10.2514/1.C034711>
- [20] S. Murugan, E. I. Saavedra Flores, S. Adhikari, M. I. Friswell, Optimal design of variable fiber spacing composites for morphing aircraft skins, *Compos. Struct.* 94 (5) (2012) 1626–1633. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2011.12.023>
- [21] C. Thill, J. A. Etches, I. P. Bond, K. D. Potter, P. M. Weaver, Composite corrugated structures for morphing wing skin applications, *Smart Mater. Struct.* 19 (12) (2010) 1–10. <https://doi.org/10.1088/0964-1726/19/12/124009>
- [22] J.-B. Bai, T.-W. Liu, G.-H. Yang, C.-C. Xie, S. Mao, A variable camber wing concept based on corrugated flexible composite skin, *Aerosp. Sci. Technol.* 138 (2023) 108318. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2023.108318>
- [23] B. Jenett, S. Calisch, D. Cellucci, N. Cramer, N. Gershenfeld, S. Swei, K. C. Cheung, Digital morphing wing: active wing shaping concept using composite lattice-

- based cellular structures, *Soft Rob.* 4 (1) (2017) 33–48. <https://doi.org/10.1089/soro.2016.0032>
- [24] D. Keidel, U. Fasel, P. Ermanni, Concept investigation of a lightweight composite lattice morphing wing, *AIAA J.* 59 (6) (2021) 2242–2250. <https://doi.org/10.2514/1.J059579>
- [25] H. Huang, Y. Fan, Z. Ke, D. Tang, W. Wang, D. Li, Designing a variable camber wing trailing edge with initially curved beams, *Aerosp. Sci. Technol.* 161 (2025) 110151. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2025.110151>
- [26] D. M. Lemos, F. D. Marques, A. J. M. Ferreira, A review on bistable composite laminates for aerospace applications, *Compos. Struct.* 329 (2024) 117756. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.compstruct.2023.117756>
- [27] J. Zhang, C. Bisagni, Buckling-driven mechanisms for twisting control in adaptive composite wings, *Aerosp. Sci. Technol.* 118 (2021) 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ast.2021.107006>
- [28] C. Bisagni, NABUCCO take-off multi-stable panels for an adaptive wing, in: 34th Congress of the International Council of the Aeronautical Sciences (ICAS2024), ICAS2024_1230, Firenze, Italy, 2024, pp. 1–9.
- [29] B. Woods, M. Friswell, Preliminary investigation of a fishbone active camber concept, in: ASME 2012 Conference on Smart Materials, Adaptive Structures and Intelligent Systems, SMASIS 2012, 2, 2012, pp. 1–9. <https://doi.org/10.1115/SMASIS2012-8058>
- [30] B. K. Woods, O. Bilgen, M. I. Friswell, Wind tunnel testing of the fish bone active camber morphing concept, *J. Intell. Mater. Syst. Struct.* 25 (7) (2014) 772–785. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1045389X14521700>
- [31] T. Mkhoyan, N. R. Thakrar, R. De Breuker, J. Sodja, Morphing wing design using integrated and distributed trailing edge morphing, *Smart Mater. Struct.* 31 (12) (2022) 125025. <https://doi.org/10.1088/1361-665X/aca18b>
- [32] J. A. Hetrick, R. F. Osborn, S. Kota, P. M. Flick, D. B. Paul, Flight testing of mission adaptive compliant wing, in: 48th AIAA/ASME/ASCE/AHS/ASC Structures, Structural Dynamics and Materials (SDM) Conference, Honolulu, Hawaii, 2007, pp. 1–18.
- [33] L. Saggere, S. Kota, Static shape control of smart structures using compliant mechanisms, *AIAA J.* 37 (5) (1999) 572–578.
- [34] K.-J. Lu, S. Kota, Design of compliant mechanisms for morphing structural shapes, *J. Intell. Mater. Syst. Struct.* 14 (2003) 379–391.
- [35] K.-J. Lu, S. Kota, An effective method of synthesizing compliant adaptive structures using load path representation, *J. Intell. Mater. Syst. Struct.* 16 (2005) 307–317.
- [36] W. Wang, F. Xi, Y. Tian, Y. Zhao, Y. Li, Modeling and analysis of a planar soft panel continuum mechanism, *J. Mech. Robot.* 12 (4) (2020) 044503. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4046029>
- [37] F. Xi, Y. Zhao, J. Wang, W. Wang, Y. Tian, Two actuation methods for a complete morphing system composed of a VGTM and a compliant parallel mechanism, *J. Mech. Robot.* 13 (2) (2021) 021020. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.4049975>
- [38] F. J. Xi, D. Oguamanam, S. Kojovic, O. Guerra, Application of mechanisms to aircraft flexible trailing edge design, in: 2024 6th International Conference on Reconfigurable Mechanisms and Robots (ReMAR), Firenze, Italy, 2024, pp. 258–264. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ReMAR61031.2024.10618077>
- [39] B. C. Prock, T. A. Weisshaar, W. A. Crossley, Morphing airfoil shape change optimization with minimum actuator energy as an objective, in: 9th AIAA/ISSMO Symposium on Multidisciplinary Analysis and Optimization, AIAA 2002, Atlanta, Georgia, 2002, p. 13.
- [40] M. C. Noviello, I. Dimino, S. Ameduri, A. Concilio, Conceptual design and topology optimization of a compliant morphing flap for next generation hybrid-electric regional aircraft, in: 34th ICAS Congress, Florence (Italy), Sept 2024, p. 10.
- [41] F. A. D'Aniello, P. Catalano, D. Quagliarella, M. Minervino, The aerodynamic design of a compliant morphing flap for next-generation hybrid electric regional aircraft, *Eng. Proc.* 90 (1) (2025). <https://doi.org/10.3390/engproc2025090013>
- [42] R. F. Osborn, S. Kota, J. A. Hetrick, D. E. Geister, C. P. Tilmann, J. Joo, Active flow control using high-frequency compliant structures, *J. Aircr.* 41 (3) (2004) 603–609. <https://doi.org/10.2514/1.111>
- [43] T. Tantanawat, S. Kota, Design of compliant mechanisms for minimizing input power in dynamic applications, *J. Mech. Des.* 129 (10) (2006) 1064–1075. <https://doi.org/10.1115/1.2756086>
- [44] B. M. Kulfan, Universal parametric geometry representation method, *J. Aircr.* 45 (1) (2008) 142–158. <https://doi.org/10.2514/1.29958>
- [45] O. A. Bauchau, J. I. Craig, *Structural Analysis: With Applications to Aerospace Structures*, Springer, 2009.
- [46] T. D. Economon, F. Palacios, S. R. Copeland, T. W. Lukaczyk, J. J. Alonso, SU2: an open-source suite for multiphysics simulation and design, *AIAA J.* 54 (3) (2016) 828–846. <https://doi.org/10.2514/1.J053813>
- [47] K.-J. Lu, S. Kota, Parameterization strategy for optimization of shape morphing compliant mechanisms using load path representation, in: ASME 2003 Design Engineering Technical Conferences and Computers and Information in Engineering Conference (DETC'03), Chicago, Illinois USA, 2003, pp. 693–702.